

Review Paper on Scheduling to Solutions: Use of MSP

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Abstract- The construction industry has witnessed a paradigm transition from manual scheduling techniques to advanced software solutions. The construction industry is grappling with the increasing complexity of project planning and management. This review explores the transition by focusing on Microsoft Project (MSP) as a dynamic tool that bridges the gap between static manual methods and modern, automated approaches. However, even when these basic methods of scheduling are used they typically incorporate errors and time is used hence not good enough to handle the new generation construction projects complexities. From critical path management through real time update, consumable resource management and dynamic modelling of schedule delay, MSP has a substantial set of function in its integrated package. The study highlights the key differences between manual techniques and MSP, emphasizing the latter's capabilities in streamlining workflows, improving collaboration, and providing actionable insights through advanced reporting tools. Comparative analysis of case studies demonstrates MSP's effectiveness in reducing project durations and costs, alongside its user-friendly interface, which enhances its adoption in diverse construction environments. It's possible that using MSP and other similar software can greatly enhance accurate planning, efficient use of resources, and reduction of delays, especially for complicated projects. The paper concludes by advocating for the broader integration of such tools in industry practice and encouraging further research to optimise their application for projects of varying scales. This shift towards technology-driven project management is essential to meeting the evolving demands of the construction sector efficiently and sustainably.

Keywords- Construction Planning, Microsoft Project (MSP), Project Management Software, Scheduling Techniques, Delay Analysis.

I. INTRODUCTION

Scheduling is the cornerstone of construction projects since it defines how best the project needs to be done, when to do it, who needs to do what and when and most important how much it is going to cost. Previously, construction activities were scheduled by use of graphical tools like Gantt charts and Critical Path Method (CPM) analysis. Such methods as these may take quite a while, are grievously imprecise and do not come with dynamic capacities essential for contemporary construction projects.^{[1][2]}

Nowadays, new generations of project management tools majorly affect the construction planning domain. all these tools, Microsoft Project has become one of the widely used solutions to scheduling, resource management, and tracking progress among others. Construction professionals cannot afford to do without powerful scheduling software that blends well with traditional construction scheduling of activities while enabling real-time adjustments and improvements, better display of the work, and a detailed report on progress.^[3]

Overview of Construction Planning and Scheduling

The construction planning and scheduling are essential aspects of construction management to facilitate the right construction undertaking by all stakeholders. This normally involves coming up with clear project goals and milestones, making work plans in form of a project schedule that outline the work to be done, the resources needed and the time to do it. Scheduling on the other hand operativity turns the plan into a timed series of activities by arranging the activities in a chronological order, allocating resources to the activities, assigning dependencies. In combination, they map how to successfully and prudently accomplish all the goals inherent in projects, including time and cost constraints or conflicting resources. The advanced planning and the scheduling from past years have not only differing methods from those of early days tactics such as hand drawn Gantt charts and the earliest stage of Critical Path Method CPM diagrams. Modern advancements such as these have allowed for real-time updates, resource optimization, and generally better visualisations which have made construction planning and scheduling with regard to the modulations of constructing projects much better equipped to handle contemporary construction ^{[4][5]}.
^[6].

Significance of Delay Analysis

Construction delay analysis is one of the critical dimensions about construction project management since its impact on the time horizon, costs and other variables related to the project. In the past, means of keeping track of delays were quite primitive, and any analysis of delay was done on slip charts, site diaries, field reports and other forms of documentation. While this was an effective approach to managing these coordination issues, it was far from efficient and more often than not, it was difficult to diagnose the problems with precision and moderate depth – the processes were slow and fragmented; it was hard to pinpoint with any degree of certainty the causes of delays or to measure the extent of their effects adequately. The absence of real-time data added to the problem since there was no way of identifying the timely corrective actions that were essential.^{[7], [8], [9].}

The use of project scheduling software like the Microsoft Project has however changed delay analysis. These tools provide accurate and timely means by which delays can be monitored and assessed where relevant scheduler details, resource deployment and status reports are Feeds directly to the system. In particular, Microsoft Project allows a user to find out critical paths, compute float and assess how the delay of a particular task influences those activities which depend on it. One advantage of scheduling simulation is that project managers can work out various what if situations in the plan and therefore come up with remedy measures for any risk that is forecasted to occur. In addition, accurate and comprehensive documentation and use of graphs enhance the presentation of delay consequences to the stakeholders and to explain the reasons for additional time required or claimed.^{[10], [11], [12].}

By transitioning to software-based solutions, construction professionals gain a more accurate and dynamic framework for delay analysis, which reduces project uncertainties and enhances decision-making processes. This evolution highlights the growing importance of leveraging technology to overcome traditional challenges and improve project outcomes.

Manual Scheduling Techniques

Other typical prior-art planning methods include the use of hand-drawn Gantt charts and planning in Excel, which is the unrefined approach to linear construction of project frameworks. However, these methods are inherently cumbersome when applied to large or complex projects because they only depend on static schedule representations that are used to manage the variability of project scope and resources, or delays that may occur along the way. In original approach the update of schedules is manual and it is always tedious task and there is high chance of errors and it is not easy to convey to all the stakeholders. Also, there is no way to control interrelated dependencies, which become more important as projects evolve and consist of numerous tasks with closely related workload and time constrains. With real-time data integration being out of the question, manual methods on the other hand fail to give a projected view of critical path, resource allocation/ utilization or the floats and therefore makes it difficult for the project managers to analysis points of delay or even model a ‘basic risk assessment’ what if???. Although the approaches used in manual scheduling enabled the evolution of modern PM practices, their flaws are noticeable which necessitated the use of advanced tools like Microsoft project whose features provide automatic and elaborate solutions to scheduling issues offering dynamic and scalable solutions that at the same time are precise in managing the complex construction projects that exist in the modern world.^{[5], [6][13].}

II. MICROSOFT PROJECT (MSP) OVERVIEW

Microsoft Project (MSP) is a complex working tool for managing project schedules that stands in-between low-tech techniques and automated processes that orient project planning. Compared to the traditional approaches such as the CPM, MSP makes things more accurate, much more flexible and efficient by adding features on it. It stands in stark contrast to traditional, time-consuming, error-laden approaches employed where MSP enables users to create, administer and track project timetables in real-time. It allows users to determine tasks, set up relationships, allocate resources, and control and visualize progress smoothly. Actually, with the help of automation features, the project manager is able to make changes regarding the work-process correspondingly to the changes in the further project requirements. Computer-based plans and icons such as Gantt charts and easy options of charts, dials let the stakeholders

see timelines and resource efficiency; thus, promoting enhanced communication. MSP also includes options like delaying analysis, resource levelling, cost control and tracking that are missing from most project management software, and hence they are crucial for handling large and complex projects. By incorporating all these features on a single interface, MSP enables teams to respond to risks effectively, improve performance, and move from conventional, paper-based and static systems to agile, virtual and dynamic systems of project management. These three luminary aspects have assisted the MSP to build itself as the most preferable system used by the construction specialists.^{[14], [15], [16]}

Microsoft Project- Key Features

Microsoft Project (MSP) is one of the most effective and flexible tools which improve the scheduling activities compared to the routine work on such.. It covers important scheduling activities so that the project managers can plan, implement and even monitor construction works of any extent with enhanced efficiency and accuracy. Flexible with resource allocation and activity scheduling: The creation of dynamic Gantt charts dramaticizes the capability of MSP to update activities, resources or even the duration where one or many of these features have been altered. MSP synchronizes with the CPM in a way that it defines the critical activities, estimates the float and plans the time line in an excellence manner while stressing on potential of delay.^[17] Resource management is yet other essential aspect that can be used to manage labour, equipment and material resources and manage workload for avoidance of overloading. The resource levelling function helps balance the resources with regard to choosing the best schedule for resource use without compromising the project duration. Further, MSP connects budgets to tasks as well as resources; it provides clients with detailed cost structures and estimates. Detailed yet flexible reporting with features such as customizable home screen make it easy to create and distribute regular status and progress reports, including on cost and risk. Through combining dynamic scheduling with resource optimization with cost control & with high value reporting, MSP turns scheduling into more of an effective and data intensive activity, assisting professionals in the construction line to manage projects better and with more confidence.^{[2], [18], [19][20]}.

Implementation of MSP in Construction:

Primarily, the current study is concerned with the management of the projects using Primavera P6 and Microsoft project known as MSP. Different issues that may arise during the construction project development from pre-construction planning phase, sequencing of activities, determination of scopes of work and responsibilities of labour, choosing of construction techniques, allocation of resources, and defining powers of the stakeholders have been considered. For this research, a residential project was selected and the costing as well as scheduling was undertaken with the help of both Primavera P6 and MSP. As it could be noted from the comparison the two tools differ only slightly. In regard to the duration of the whole project, MSP indicated 93 days while the Primavera that was used in calculations proposed 87 days. Likewise in the cost analysis, as under: Using MSP the total cost of the project was ₹ 13,34,345 whereas by using the Primavera it was ₹13,82,573. From the comparison of the parameters of the two software tools the former seemed slightly better and much more friendly than the latter. The survey shows that in countries like India, software based project handling is mostly used in large construction projects of sizeable proportions and limited use or complete absence of software is evident in small construction projects. The performing features of both Primavera P6 and MSP include the following which show their capacities and specialization in specific tasks in project management. From this research, the effectiveness of both these tools is highlighted, from generalized project planning to management of larger-scale projects. Finally, it postulates that to implement small, medium, or large scale construction projects, it is necessary to select the appropriate software depending on the requirement and scope of the work to be done since each of the above-mentioned tools may not work in the same efficient manner^[21]. Technology keeps on changing from one period to the other and has played a great role in transforming construction management. There are now many specific application programs available to assist in the many construction management processes this of most importance to implementing the schedule and data. These programs help in such functions as entering project details, scheduling activities, report writing and monitoring of project progress. One of such application was used in Lamreung Limpok Bridge in Lamgapan, Aceh Besar, Aceh, Indonesia. Before it became a part of the newly implemented trans-Aceh

roads network in 2018, this bridge construction project was financed by the Aceh Government Budget with a total cost of Rp. 27,179,501,000. The construction of this bridge was planned to be I launched in 141 working days, but today it is an important link between the areas of Ulee Kareng and Limpok. The project involved eight key activity parameters: general work, drainage, land-related work, aggregate pavement, asphalt pavement, structure, finishing, and maintenance. The area of concern regarding this study was the problem of project implementation scheduling through redesigning of project schedule using Microsoft Project 2013. The change in the schedule also showed a cut in the project duration to be 122 working days. Moreover, the Gantt Chart and PDM were also conventional and professionally developed to manage the project and execute its steps. This case reveals how advanced construction management technologies can be deployed to enhance the management of project programmes and consequently achieve more desirable results ^[14].

III. ANALYSIS OF DELAYS IN CONSTRUCTION PROJECTS

Delays can be separated into excusable or non-excusable, compensable or non-compensable, and concurrent delays each of which occur for different reasons and affect construction projects in terms of time and cost. Microsoft Project (MSP) alleviates these challenges by presenting a more efficient and mechanized method of delay analysis. MSP's dynamic scheduling engine helps users to track the dependencies, recognize the critical path and specific delays that have occurred and also to determine the differences in the time lines immediately. The core basic components which are the baselines and variance analysis enables the identification of the deviation from the set schedule and the cause of such delay. MSP unifies real-time data of delays and automates the tracking process, thus resembling project performance details requiring much less time and effort for analysis. Such a shift to a software-based technique also guarantees improvement in the accuracy, accountability, and sensitivity of the treatment of delay in contemporary construction projects ^{[7], [8], [9], [22], [23]}.

Overcoming Delays and Improving Scheduling-

Microsoft Project (MSP) offers a sound solution for managing and overcoming delays, that I have discovered whilst conducting this research, which working with manual systems, cannot overcome. Detecting the sources of delay with or without IT support is often a tedious exercise that involves a lot of effort to generate new schedules for the project activities, to assess the consequent changes, and to prepare measures to overcome the sources of delay. ANOTHER is that it is not flexible enough to handle real time changes hence proactive handling of these issues is complex. MSP counters these limitations with some of the most developed tools that enhance the management of delay practices ^[24]. Its dynamic scheduling engine instantly recalculates project timelines when delays happen, updating activities and dependencies on the critical path. This lets project managers quickly see how delays affect the schedule and figure out what changes need to be made ^[25]. MSP possesses control over the resource allocation as well as levelling that helps in defining workloads and smashing up troubles that slow down solutions forcefully repudiate project period expectations. It also has "What if" Analysis of the schedule that allows the teams to change the ways of doing things to fit the time constraints of the undertaking such as moving around the activities or executing some of the critical activities faster in order to eliminate anticipations. With progress tracking so that it is against baselines, MSP assists the project managers in identifying signals that there might be a problem in that they can correct these problems before they lead to complications. Along with extensive reporting tools, MSP helps to minimize the impact of delay and thus is an essential tool to control project schedules in the scope of highly changing and unpredictable conditions ^{[26][27][28]}

IV. COMPARISON OF MANUAL SCHEDULING VS. MICROSOFT PROJECT (MSP)

Compared to the past, the sophistication in creating, supervising, and organizing schedules has undergone severe improvement because of project management tools. The exact area that differentiates between the older process of manual scheduling and newer tools in the form of MSP, or Microsoft Project. Again and again, literature reviews state that organizations demand increased precision, scope, and adaptability in managing multifaceted projects, at which traditional processes fail. Manual methods laid the basis for project scheduling, however, not being sufficient to reflect all the parameters, track the

progress or analyze delays, automated methods were incorporated. Thanks to the capabilities of MSP and its main functions, it is considered to be one of the leading products available on the market. Its features makes processes less complicated, increases collaboration, and increases its efficiency, which is completely opposite as informal systems are rigid and have tendencies to be erroneous. This comparison seek to elaborate these differences with a view of illustrating the need to adopt and transform to the use of modern project management tools. The following are the detailed findings of this comparison.

TABLE I
COMPARISON OF MANUAL SCHEDULING VS. MICROSOFT PROJECT (MSP)

Aspect	Manual Scheduling	Microsoft Project (MSP)
Accuracy	Prone to human errors, especially in calculations and task dependencies.	Automated calculations ensure accurate task dependencies, durations, and critical path analysis.
Real-Time Tracking	There is no real-time tracking; updates require manual intervention, which can be time-consuming.	There is real-time tracking; updates require intervention, which can be easy.
Scalability	The system has limited scalability, making it challenging to manage complex projects with multiple tasks and dependencies.	The system effortlessly expands to manage extensive, intricate projects that involve multiple activities and dependencies.
Collaboration	Challenging to share and collaborate effectively; updates may not be synchronised.	Supports team collaboration with shared access and synchronised updates in real time.
Delay Analysis	Manually identifying delays and their impact requires significant effort.	Tools for automated delay tracking and analysis, including variance reports and baseline comparisons, are available.
Resource Management	Difficult to track and optimize resource allocation manually.	Includes resource leveling and optimization features to prevent overallocation or conflicts.
Visualization	Static Gantt charts and schedules; updates must be redrawn manually.	Dynamic Gantt charts and other visualizations update automatically as changes occur.
Time and Effort	High time and effort required to update schedules and manage dependencies.	Reduces time and effort with automated updates and task management tools.
Flexibility	Limited flexibility to adapt to changes or simulate "what-if" scenarios.	Enables flexibility with scenario simulations and dynamic adjustments.
Reporting	Basic or non-standardized reporting; often requires additional effort to compile data.	Generates detailed, standardized reports with minimal effort.

Research Gap

Current construction planning and management has greatly benefitted from the evolution of manual scheduling from software solutions like the Microsoft Project (MSP). The paper lays out how MSP resolves the inherent difficulties with the static matrix in dealing with the agile strategies, scheduling ability, real-time performance, and resource optimization. ; thus, MSP optimizes project-centered operations, team cooperation, and problem-solving by combining critical path management and dynamic delay modeling. By employing such software, operational costs are reduced, as well as the time it takes to achieve a given objective as supported by many examples. However, the paper also found some research limitations though the proposed method enhances the MS scheduling performance significantly, such as, the fact that, the application of the MSP under consideration is project type dependent; that the proposed MSP has to be integrated with other construction management tools. Consequently, studying long-term outcomes regarding the MSP performance and its predictors, the barriers to the adoption of MSP, and the use of the MSP system in sustainable construction also indicates promising directions for future research in the field of construction management.

V. CONCLUSION

The transition from manual ways of working to scheduling software such as Microsoft Project (MSP) represents a significant leap in the

project management world. Manual methods are still with us, but their limitations are becoming clearer. They rely on static schedules that can't really be called schedules at all; they're more like Gantt charts mounted on the walls of the project manager's office. And while such a wall-mounted schedule isn't really dynamic, at least it can be tracked with a certain level of efficiency that manual methods just can't muster. In contrast to these wall charts is the Microsoft Project "Gantt view," which can be updated in real time,

and which, because it can be linked to a "resource report," provides the basis for a "delay analysis," which can be better understood in terms of "resource leveling."

The construction industry must decisively move away from manual scheduling methods in favor of automated scheduling tools, with the clear benefits of software-based solutions, such as Microsoft Project, long established. There are two primary reasons for this. First, manual tools cannot match the speed and accuracy of automated tools. Second, even if manual methods could somehow increase the speed and accuracy of planning and scheduling processes, these same manual methods are incapable of achieving the requisite efficiency in the push to satisfy the various stakeholders who must be involved in the planning and scheduling of construction projects—enough efficiency, in other words, to deal with the push for better productivity associated by the construction stakeholders with the industry.

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